

Fracture toughness of graphene sheet estimated by coupling of boundary element and finite element

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Introduction (1/5)

- ◆ **Stiffness, strength and fracture toughness**
 - **Definition in continuum mechanics**

- To predict **stiffness**: stress-strain relation can be **linear**, and hence harmonic potential can be used.
- To predict **strength and fracture toughness**: stress-strain relation should be **non-linear**, and an appropriate potential energy function describing the interactions of atoms is necessary.

Introduction (2/5)

◆ Prediction of stiffness

■ Experimental works such as *atomic force microscopy*

Treacy, et al., 1996; Wong, et al., 1997; Krishnan, et al., 1998; Salvetat, et al., 1999; Yu, et al., 2000.

■ Theoretical and numerical simulation

◆ *Atomic modeling*

- *ab initio* method (Sanchez-Portal, et al., 1999; Faccio, 2009; Lier, et al., 2000)
- lattice-dynamical model (Popov and Van Doren, 2000)
- molecular dynamics simulation (Lu, 1997; Cornwell and Wille, 1997; Jin and Yuan, 2003; Liew, et al., 2004; Bao, et al., 2004; Agrawal, et al., 2006)

◆ *Continuum modeling*

- structural mechanics finite element method (Li and Chou, 2003; Fan, et al., 2009)
- nanoscale continuum theory or called analytical molecular mechanics model (Zhang, et al., 2002; Chang and Gao, 2003; Natsuki, et al., 2004; Xiao, et al., 2005; Chang, et al., 2006; Shokrieh and Rafiee, 2010)
- molecular-continuum model (Hwu and Yeh, 2014)

Introduction (3/5)

◆ Prediction of strength and fracture toughness

- Unlike stiffness, relative fewer studies can be found for the prediction of strength and toughness of nanomaterials (Belytschko et al., 2002; Liew et al., 2004; Xu, 2009; Wang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2012).

◆ Molecular-continuum model

- The molecular-continuum model was proposed to estimate the **stiffness** of graphene and CNTs (Hwu and Yeh, 2014), and later was extended to the estimation of **strength and fracture toughness** (Yeh and Hwu, 2017; 2019).
- The key concept of this model is the connection of **molecular dynamics and continuum mechanics** through *the equivalence of potential energy of molecules and strain energy of continuum*.

Introduction (4/5)

◆ Multiscale simulation via coupling of BEM and FEM

- A new approach of multi-scale simulation via **coupling of boundary element and finite element** is proposed to predict the fracture toughness of graphene sheet.
- In this simulation a **molecular dynamics-based nonlinear beam element** is developed for the *atomistic model near the crack tip*, whereas a **two-dimensional special boundary element** is employed for the *continuum model in the remaining field of the cracked specimen*.

◆ Estimation of the required properties used in FEM and BEM

- The **material and section properties** required in the *nonlinear beam element* are estimated through the **equivalence** between the *potential energy of molecular dynamics* and the *elastic strain energy of continuum mechanics*.
- With the estimated properties of beam element, the **material properties of the boundary element** are further estimated by applying loads on the specimen of graphene, which is formed by a **hexagonal lattice of carbon atoms**.

Introduction (5/5)

◆ Local-global concept for multiscale simulation

- Coupling the nonlinear beam elements by boundary elements with the **local-global** concept of multi-scaled simulation, a vast of computational time can be saved.

◆ Prediction of crack propagation

- The accuracy of **near tip stresses** obtained in our simulation *remedies the inaccuracy of linear elastic fracture mechanics*, and can be used for the prediction of **atomic bond-breaking**, which leads to **crack propagation**.

◆ Prediction of fracture toughness

- The associated **critical load** can then be applied in the **continuum model** for the cracked specimen to predict **mode I and mode II fracture toughness** of graphene.
- The obtained values were then *verified* by the published results measured or predicted by the other methods [1-5].
- By *varying the size of cracks and orientation of applied loads*, several interesting phenomena have been observed and discussed in this work.

Coupling of BEM and FEM (1/2)

- ◆ A molecular dynamics-based nonlinear beam element
 - for the atomistic model near the crack tip
- ◆ A two-dimensional special boundary element
 - for the continuum model in the remaining field of the cracked specimen.

Figure 6. A cracked specimen of graphene subjected to uniform load.

Coupling of BEM and FEM (2/2)

- ◆ Atomistic model for a cracked graphene
 - Zigzag orientation
 - Armchair orientation

Figure 7. Atomistic model of a cracked graphene; (a) zigzag orientation, (b) armchair orientation.

Nonlinear Beam Element (1/3)

◆ **Material properties** required in nonlinear beam element

- Estimated through the equivalence between the **potential energy** of molecular dynamics and the **elastic strain energy** of continuum mechanics.

Bond stretching energy of atoms (a) Stretching energy of beams

Angle variation energy of atoms (b) Bending energy of beams

Figure 1. Equivalence between interatomic energy of molecular mechanics and strain energy of beam element.

Nonlinear Beam Element (2/3)

◆ Material properties required in nonlinear beam element

- To describe the interatomic interaction of graphene, the **modified Morse potential energy function** U is considered.

$$U = D_e [1 - e^{-\beta(\Delta\ell)}]^2 + \frac{1}{2} k_\theta (\Delta\theta)^2 [1 + k_s (\Delta\theta)^4]$$

- The **interactive force** F can be derived as

$$F(\Delta\ell) = \frac{\partial U}{\partial(\Delta\ell)} = 2\beta D_e (1 - e^{-\beta(\Delta\ell)}) e^{-\beta(\Delta\ell)}$$

- The **stress-strain relation** required in the nonlinear beam element can now be obtained as

$$\sigma(\varepsilon) = \frac{2\beta D_e}{A} (1 - e^{-\beta\varepsilon\ell_0}) e^{-\beta\varepsilon\ell_0}$$

Nonlinear Beam Element (3/3)

◆ Section properties required in nonlinear beam element

- Using the *nonlinear stress-strain relation* and assuming a *circular cross section* of radius R_b for the beam, **deduction of classical beam theory** leads to

$$M = \int \sigma y dA = \frac{1}{2} D_e \beta^2 R_b^2 \Delta\theta \left[1 + \frac{7}{12} \beta^2 R_b^2 (\Delta\theta)^2 + \frac{31}{384} \beta^2 R_b^2 (\Delta\theta)^4 + \dots \right].$$

- The **interactive moment M** derived by modified Morse potential energy function U

$$M(\Delta\theta) = \frac{\partial U}{\partial(\Delta\theta)} = k_\theta \Delta\theta [1 + 3k_s (\Delta\theta)^4].$$

- By comparison, we see that the most proper cross section for the modeling of nonlinear beam element is the one with $R_b = 0.063$ nm.

Figure 2. Variation of bending moment with respect to bond angle.

Special Boundary Element (1/2)

◆ Material properties required in boundary element

- Homogenized mechanical properties of graphene
- To estimate the mechanical properties such as Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, a tensile force F in the x -direction is applied on the specimen of graphene, which is formed by hexagonal lattice of carbon atoms

$$E = \frac{\sigma_x}{\varepsilon_x} = \frac{F / A}{\Delta L / L} = \frac{FL}{A\Delta L},$$

$$\nu = -\frac{\varepsilon_y}{\varepsilon_x} = -\frac{\Delta W / W}{\Delta L / L} = -\frac{L\Delta W}{W\Delta L},$$

Special Boundary Element (2/2)

◆ Special boundary element method (SBEM):

- The fundamental solution of SBEM has satisfied the **traction-free crack** boundary conditions and hence **no meshes are required along the crack surfaces**.

Figure 5. BEM continuum model for a cracked graphene sheet under different loading conditions: (a) tensile load, (b) pure shear.

Evaluation of stress intensity factors (1/2)

- ◆ The stress intensity factors are usually defined as

$$\mathbf{k} = \begin{Bmatrix} K_{II} \\ K_I \\ K_{III} \end{Bmatrix} = \lim_{\substack{r \rightarrow 0 \\ \theta = 0}} \sqrt{2\pi r} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{23} \end{Bmatrix}$$

To avoid the inaccuracy around the near tip, two different methods are used:

- Evaluation by using the remote boundary displacements and tractions (Hwu and Liang, 2000; Hwu, et al, 2017)

$$\mathbf{k} = \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \left[\mathbf{R}_2^* \mathbf{G}_{n1}^c + \mathbf{T}^* \mathbf{G}_{n2}^c \right] \mathbf{t}_n - \left[\mathbf{R}_2^* \mathbf{Y}_{n1}^c + \mathbf{T}^* \mathbf{Y}_{n2}^c \right] \mathbf{u}_n \right\}$$

- Evaluation by the path-independent H-integral (Hwu and Kuo, 2007; Hwu and Huang, 2012)

$$H = \int_{\Gamma} (\mathbf{u}^T \hat{\mathbf{t}} - \hat{\mathbf{u}}^T \mathbf{t}) ds \quad \mathbf{k} = \Lambda \mathbf{H}^{*-1} \mathbf{h}$$

Evaluation of stress intensity factors (2/2)

- Remote boundary displacements and tractions & integral path for path-independent H-integral

Figure 5. Location of boundary nodes for eqn.(12), and the integral path for H-integral.

Failure Criterion

- ◆ The failure occurs when the stress reaches its ultimate value whose associated strain is then used to be the **critical strain** for the failure criterion
- ◆ In other words, when the **distance between two atoms** is greater than a critical length, the bonding force is too weak to maintain the connection of the atoms, and the **bond breaks**.

Figure 3. Stress-strain relation of a nonlinear beam element; (a) a curve from the stretching energy of the C-C bond in molecular dynamics, (b) a curve for the input data required in ANSYS.

Numerical Results – Fracture toughness of graphene (1/2)

- ◆ Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness for graphene in zigzag or armchair orientation.

Numerical Results – Fracture toughness of graphene (2/2)

- ◆ Comparison with the results obtained by the other methods.

Table 3: Mode I and mode II fracture toughness of graphene by various methods.

Toughness (MPa \sqrt{m})	Mode-I (zigzag)	Mode-I (armchair)	Mode-II (zigzag)	Mode-II (armchair)
Present Study	3.25	3.97	2.4	3.8
Experiment ¹⁶	4.0 \pm 0.6	-	-	-
Coupled QM/CM ¹⁸	4.21	3.71	-	-
Coupled QM/MM ¹⁷	-	3.3-4.0	-	-
MD & REBO potential ²¹	3.05	3.38	3.06	2.87
MC Model ²⁴	1.99-2.54	3.13-3.71	3.73-4.45	2.70-2.89

Numerical Results – Crack Propagation (1/2)

- ◆ Propagation path of a zigzag crack in graphene with initial crack length $a=0.15W$ under different loading directions.

Numerical Results – Crack Propagation (2/2)

- ◆ Propagation path of an armchair crack in graphene with a specified loading direction under different initial crack lengths.

Conclusions

- ◆ **Multiscale simulation by coupling of BEM and FEM**
 - By coupling of SBEM for global field and nonlinear beam element for local field, **mode I and mode II fracture toughness** as well as **crack propagation path** in a single layer graphene sheet were predicted.
- ◆ **Accuracy and efficiency**
 - The plane dimension of graphene is considered **in the scale of 0.1mm*0.1mm**, whereas the failure criterion is made on the C-C bond whose length is only **0.142nm**. If the entire field is simulated by nonlinear beam element, over billions of atoms are involved. By using the proposed multiscale simulation, only ?? elements are used in SBEM and less than 6500 atoms are involved in our atomistic model for the subdomain of graphene, and hence **a vast of computational time** are saved.
 - Generally for the prediction of fracture toughness it takes less than 3 minutes on Intel Core i7-6700 CPU 3.40-340GHz computer processor.
- ◆ **Crack propagation pattern**
 - depends on the initial crack length under the various loading conditions.

Thank you for your attention!!

